

Synthesis and Characterisation of Xanthate Anions as Salts of Bis(cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) Chelates formed with 2,3-Dihydroxy Pyridine and 2-Amino-3-hydroxy Pyridine

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A number of workers¹ have found that coordination of four oxygen or two oxygen and two nitrogen atoms by strong covalent bonds to the Cp_2Zr^{2+} (IV) moiety, leads to weakening of the metal-ring bonds. In order to investigate whether the coordination of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) ligands, two molecules of which can have four oxygen atoms and two oxygen and two nitrogen atoms respectively, with Cp_2Zr^{2+} would lead to similar weakening of metal-ring bond, we tried the reaction of the uninegative bidentate ligands, 2,3-dihydroxypyridine² (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine³ (AHP) with Cp_2ZrCl_2 in aqueous medium in M to L ratio of 1 : 1 and soluble complex species so formed were further reacted with xanthate anions ($ROCS_2^-$, where R=Me, Et or i-Pr) resulting in the formation of insoluble salts. These salts were characterised by elemental analysis, conductance measurements, ir and pmr spectral studies.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are thermally stable decomposing at higher temperature without melting. These compounds are moderately soluble in nitrobenzene, methanol and deuterated acetone. The molar conductance values show that all the complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes.

The ir spectra of the compounds show usual peaks for $\eta^5 C_5H_5$ group¹: at 3 085 (C-H stretching), 1 430 (C-C asymmetric ring breathing mode of π -bond), 1 035 (C-H in-plane bending vibration) and 815 cm^{-1} (C-H bending out-of-plane deformation). Apart from this an additional band near 440 cm^{-1} can be assigned to Zr-C₅H₅ vibration⁵.

In DHP a broad band found at 3 200 cm^{-1} due to hydrogen bonding disappeared in all the complexes, showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of Zr-O bond at 3-position. A strong band at 1 625 cm^{-1}

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd	HL*	Yield %	Colour	Dec. temp. °C	Elemental analysis : Found / (Calcd.)					Molar cond $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$
						Zr	C	H	N	S	
1	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [MeOCS_2]^-$	DHP	69	Light brown	275	20.68 (20.77)	46.67 (46.45)	3.58 (3.87)	3.22 (3.18)	14.71 (14.77)	29.5
2	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [EtOCS_2]^-$	DHP	68	Brown	289	20.27 (20.13)	47.38 (47.65)	4.47 (4.19)	3.14 (3.08)	14.47 (14.32)	28.6
3	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [i-PrOCS_2]^-$	DHP	69	Dark brown	306	19.46 (19.52)	48.98 (48.80)	4.26 (4.49)	2.92 (2.99)	13.82 (13.89)	28.4
4	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [MeOCS_2]^-$	AHP	68	Greyish brown	264	20.89 (20.82)	46.23 (46.56)	4.26 (4.10)	6.31 (6.39)	14.76 (14.81)	30.2
5	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [EtOCS_2]^-$	AHP	67	Brown	275	20.24 (20.17)	47.53 (47.77)	4.76 (4.42)	6.12 (6.19)	14.42 (14.35)	29.6
6	$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ [i-PrOCS_2]^-$	AHP	67	Dark brown	290	19.44 (19.57)	48.62 (48.91)	4.52 (4.71)	6.08 (6.80)	13.99 (13.92)	28.4

*DHP = 2, 3-Dihydroxypyridine. AHP=2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine.

assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ shifted to lower side in the complexes suggesting that the ligand coordinates to metal through oxygen of carbonyl group at its 2-position. A relatively weak band at 3400 cm^{-1} observed in the free DHP and attributed to ν_{NH} of α -pyridone like structure of DHP remained unchanged in the complexes, suggesting its non-involvement in coordination.

In the ir spectra of AHP a ν_{OH} (O-H--N) band found at 3425 cm^{-1} disappeared in the complexes showing the simultaneous deprotonation and formation of Zr-O at 3-position of the ligand. Two other bands found at 3375 and 3125 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{NH} asymmetric and ν_{NH} symmetric vibrations respectively. Symmetric band shifted to $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes indicating the formation of Zr-N bonding at 2-position of the ligand.

In both the DHP and AHP complexes, bands found at $490\text{--}540$ and $470\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ further confirm Zr-O⁶ and Zr-N⁷ bondings.

From the detailed investigation of ir spectra of various xanthate compounds, it is concluded that there are two characteristic bands for xanthate group: the band at $1010\text{--}1020$ (C=S) and $1240\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O)⁸.

In the pmr spectra of the complexes, the resonance signal due to C₅H₅ group occurred at $\delta\sim 6.60$. The existence of single sharp C₅H₅ resonance is attributed to rapid rotation of ring about metal-ring axis⁹.

In case of the DHP and AHP complexes, the values of chemical shifts ($\delta\sim 1.72, \sim 1.80, \sim 2.60, \sim 1.82$) of protons of chelated DHP and chemical shifts ($\sim 3.40, \sim 1.80, \sim 2.72, \sim 7.32$) of protons of AHP indicate that there is bonding of zirconium through oxygen and oxygen atoms and oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the ligands respectively.

The resonance signals of the alkyl group(s) in the xanthate moiety occur at almost same chemical shifts as for the free xanthate ligand. The intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The integrated proton ratios correspond to the formula assigned to these compounds.

From the above studies it can be concluded that the ligand DHP or AHP is chelating with (Cp)₂Zr²⁺ having a wedge like sandwich structure with essentially tetrahedral coordination about the metal atom similar to that of dichloride¹⁰ and xanthate anions are forming salts with the [(Cp)₂ZrL]⁺ complex cationic species.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Cp₂ZrCl₂ (Fluka) and DHP and AHP (both Aldrich) were used. Potassium salts of alkyl xanthates were prepared by the reported method¹¹.

Microanalyses were carried out in Microanalytical Laboratory, Delhi University. Nitrogen, sulphur and zirconium were estimated by standard methods¹².

Conductance measurements were made in nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M) with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room temperature. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ((CD₃)₂CO) at a sweep width of 60 MHz and a sweep time of 300s on a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer R-600 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference.

Preparation of compounds: To an aqueous solution (50 ml) of Cp₂ZrCl₂ (0.0730 g, 5 mmol), DHP/AHP (0.0277 g / 0.0275 g, 5 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2–3 h. Any resulting precipitate was removed by filtration. The filtrate was then added dropwise with continuous stirring to a concentrated hot aqueous solution of appropriate potassium xanthate (5 mmol; potassium *o*-methylxanthate, potassium *o*-ethylxanthate, potassium *o*-isopropylxanthate). The precipitate so obtained was digested over a water-bath at $60\text{--}70^{\circ}$ for 2 h, filtered, washed with hot water and dried in vacuum over P₂O₁₀.

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